

Behavioral Economics in Public Policy in the Age of Covid-19: A Systematic Review

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Issue Details**Issue Title:** Issue 2**Received:** 25 March, 2021**Accepted:** 27 April, 2021**Published:** 15 May, 2021

Pages: 1533 - 1546

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Linguistica Antverpiensia

Abstract

Following the guidelines of the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement and accessing databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar and Academic Search, during the years 2020 and 2021, with topics related to behavioral economics and the design of public policies to address the covid-19 pandemic, it has been determined that public policy makers have identified behavioral biases that have impeded rational decision making by individuals regarding vaccination, the use of personal protection mechanisms such as masks and face shields, social distancing, dietary habits and physical activity. The behavioral biases identified have been mainly loss aversion related to negativity framing bias, representativeness heuristics, confirmation bias, present bias, negativity bias, over-optimism, availability heuristics, status quo or inertia bias and cognitive overload. The tools with the greatest application to combat behavioral biases have been framing, used in communication mechanisms, financial or in-kind micro-incentives for compliance, descriptive and prescriptive norms, as well as nudges and libertarian paternalism. Finally, there is evidence that behavioral economics has a substantial contribution to make in the fight against the covid-19 pandemic and the scenario is serving to validate the contributions of the 2017 Nobel Laureate in Economics Richard H. Thaler.

Keywords: behavioral economics, public policy, covid-19.

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic caused by Covid-19 has impacted the different dimensions of life in society. In addition to the increase in mortality rates in almost all countries since 2020, there has been a saturation of the various health systems, a crisis in education systems and economic losses that have slowed the growth of the least developed countries. In this context, governments have been adopting different measures to reduce the spread of the disease, from closing their borders to imposing quarantines and mandatory use of masks. For this, public policies need to be effective, efficient and effective, requiring a guiding framework that considers one of the most important factors in this fight, people's behavior, a reason that leads to review the contributions of two fundamental disciplines, psychology and economics, which converge in what is known as "behavioral economics", considered by Thaler(2018) as "a return to the kind of open-minded and intuitively motivated discipline invented by Adam Smith and expanded by increasingly powerful statistical tools and databases" (p. 40).

In line with the recognition made by Pérez Martínez & Rodríguez Fernández (2020), who consider that behavioral economics has potential for adaptation and application in public policies and given the variety of actions of the State to face the crisis at a global level, it is necessary to systematize the information and determine to what extent and modalities behavioral economics has been used to guide the actions of citizens on issues such as social distancing, mandatory confinements, acceptance of vaccines, hygiene practices, among others.

With respect to the development of economics as a social science, an evolution over time can be observed. The contributions of Adam Smith (1776), considered as the father of political economy, who based his theories on the natural order of things and human freedoms, with foundations from philosophy, law and mathematics, then there have been contributions from statistics that together with economic theory and mathematics gave way to econometrics and from there the development of microeconomics and macroeconomics. The most recent advances are those inspired by psychology, as in the case of behavioral economics (Tejedor-Estupiñán, 2020).

Adam Smith's contributions related to the concepts of loss aversion, overconfidence, altruism, equity, among others, give a clear vision that agents do not always behave rationally, but with multidimensionality and realism (Ashraf, Camerer and Loewenstein 2005, cited in Tejedor-Estupiñán, 2020).

In 2017, Richard H. Thaler consolidated his contributions on behavioral theory by being awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics, three years after Daniel Kahneman received the same award in the same line of theoretical development. This new vision considers that human beings do not behave as classical economists claim, i.e., rationally, defining them as *Homo economicus*. Behavioral economics considers that there is a series of behavioral biases, in addition to bounded rationality, that indicates the presence of a *Homo sapiens*, also known as human.

There are important contributions on how cognitive, psychological and social factors influence the irrational behavior of human beings when making decisions, which cannot be modeled by mathematics and statistics. This view contrasts with the neoclassical view, which is based on utility maximization. Tools have been identified to deal with behavioral biases to induce proper decision making, nudging being the main one, to cope with the cognitive costs of absorbing information in the propagation of the COVID 19 virus (Llonto Caicedo & Vela Meléndez, 2021).

The systematic biases present in decision making, which underpin behavioral economics, are the following: The law of small numbers, i.e. people tend to generalize results with small samples, also present is the anchor effect, which is manifested when a person's decisions are influenced by a previous information he received, regardless of the relevance of the same, another important bias is the availability bias which are the errors made when using the availability heuristic, the "shortenings" of the path that the mind makes to reach answers, in this case there are influences of facts reported by the media or recent

experiences lived by individuals. Also important is the confirmatory bias, i.e., the validity given by individuals to accept facts that confirm what they think (Almeida Hernández, 2020).

The knowledge of these systematic biases that confirm the bounded rationality are important for the design of State action strategies and to induce behaviors that allow fighting against the pandemic that is in full development.

In this context, this paper aims to identify the adoption of behavioral economics in public policies to address the covid-19 pandemic.

The first part of the document contains an introduction with the theoretical foundations and the purpose of the research, followed by the methodology of the systematic review based on the PRISMA statement and, in the final part, the results, discussion and conclusions.

METHODOLOGY

The systematic review was developed following the guidelines of the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement. The information was collected from databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, Google Scholar and Academic Search, identifying 159 documents that were published between 2020 and 2021. The search process was carried out using protocols according to the databases such as: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("behavioral economics") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (covid-19) in Scopus, TI= (behavioral economics AND covid-19) in Web of Science, intitle: "behavioral economics" AND covid-19 in Google Scholar and (behavioral economics) AND (public policy) AND covid-19 in PubMed. After applying inclusion criteria such as linkage to key terms like behavioral or behavioral economics, public policy and covid-19, as well as excluding duplicates and those with methodological weaknesses, 18 papers were determined to pass to systematic review (See figure 1).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Of the studies analyzed, 61% have a positivist approach and mainly use online surveys as well as experiments. The latter techniques are common in behavioral economics. Thirty-nine percent have an interpretative hermeneutic approach, using documentary analysis techniques and some with other qualitative designs such as phenomenological ones through focus groups. This higher proportion of experimental quantitative studies is consistent because this development of economic science analyzes irrational decisions and the errors that are made in this process, which are referred to as heuristics and biases; and, instead of using the assumptions of the theory of rationality, it resorts to experimental psychology data and neuroscience data on everything that are economic behaviors (Rodriguez Cairo, 2018). These experimental designs with empirical measurement are conducted using large-scale randomized controlled trials in field settings (Haushofer et al., 2020).

Regarding the measures taken by the States to face the pandemic, in whose public policies behavioral economics has been used or those that are susceptible to management with this theoretical development, vaccination campaigns stand out (Haushofer et al., 2020; Hursh et al., 2020; Saleska & Choi, 2021; Strickland et al., 2021; Wagner et al., 2020), social distancing norms (Haushofer et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Lunn et al., 2020; Soofi et al., 2020; Strickland et al., 2021), use of face masks and face shields (Liu et al., 2020; Si et al., 2021; Strickland et al., 2021), hygiene practices and coughing/sneezing rules (Haushofer et al., 2020), and confinement rules (Liu et al., 2020).

According to Haushofer et al.(2020), behavioral economics has made relevant contributions in identifying approaches and tools to improve the level of adherence to these behaviors, especially in environments with greater precariousness, where a greater impact of virus outbreaks is foreseeable. However, even so, the essentially dynamic nature of epidemics has not been fully exploited.

There are important contributions aligned with the findings of this research, which speak of the need to overcome the limits imposed by the schematic vision of positivism, rationalism and determinism, when conceiving human nature. "The social sciences have to encourage the critical analysis of these conditions and project the mechanisms that guarantee an existence in the new environment, based on interdisciplinarity and the complex approach in the analysis of reality" (Pérez Martínez & Rodríguez Fernández, 2020, p. 507). Therefore, it is concluded that behavioral economics has an important potential for use in public policies to induce adequate behaviors of people.

Behavioral biases that have been identified and are amenable to interventions using behavioral economics are: Loss aversion related to the negativity bias in framing, in this regard people tend to be more attentive to negative information than positive information and therefore perceptions tend to be "stickier", "we are less likely to change our minds about something we perceive negatively than about something we perceive positively" (Saleska & Choi, 2021, p. 3). In a complementary way are the contributions of (Plaksienko et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2020) related to underuse of vaccines and overuse of antimicrobials. On the other hand, studies show that in dealing with the pandemic, biases such as representativeness heuristics, confirmation bias, present bias, negativity bias, over-optimism, availability heuristics, status quo or inertia bias, and cognitive overload have been identified (Saleska & Choi, 2021; Si et al., 2021; Soofi et al., 2020).

**Figure 2. Sankey diagram with behavioral biases identified in review documents.
Own elaboration in ATLAS.ti 9**

This research identified that some tools are of greater use by public policy makers to attack behavioral biases. Among the most recurrent are framing, used in communication mechanisms (Ayres et al., 2020; Halpern et al., 2020; Hursh et al., 2020; Soofi et al., 2020; Strickland et al., 2021). These findings are consistent with studies published by the Inter-American Development Bank where it mentions that "In the graph [...] shows the gains from less interaction with other people" (Martinez et al., 2020, p. 15), i.e., communication mechanisms with graphs allow people to make better decisions because they observe how images that show social distancing generate results. Microincentives have also been used, in this regard "it has been identified that small financial or in-kind incentives, such as a bag of lentils given for vaccinating children, or a small payment for collecting HIV test results, increase these behaviors" (Banerjee, Duflo, Glennerster, & Kothari, 2010; Thornton, 2008, cited in Haushofer et al., 2020, pp. 2-3), in the same vein are findings related to government payments to those who comply with social distancing instructions or confinements "are designed to compensate them for the costs of taking such prosocial precautions. Of course, there is a risk of mismatches: people receiving the payments who

nevertheless fail to comply with the distancing and quarantine guidelines." (Robertson et al., 2020, p. 13).

On the other hand, studies have been identified that consider descriptive norms (Si et al., 2021; Wagner et al., 2020), heuristics (Llonto Caicedo & Vela Meléndez, 2021), salience (Lunn et al., 2020), prescriptive norms (Liu et al., 2020), nudges (Pérez Martínez & Rodríguez Fernández, 2020; Soofi et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2020), libertarian paternalism (LlontoCaicedo & Vela Meléndez, 2021; Pérez Martínez & Rodríguez Fernández, 2020). Regarding the latter tools, it is necessary to mention that according to Sunstein and Thaler, 2017, cited in Rodriguez, 2018) regarding Libertarian Paternalism, they state the following: Taking Milton Friedman's expression "libertarian paternalists want people to be "free to choose",and aspire to design policies that maintain or enhance freedom of choice (...). Libertarian paternalism is a relatively weak and soft type of paternalism", they state in this way since it does not involve meddling, but the activation of small nudges that constitute aspects of the architecture of decisions that modifies people's behavior in a predictable way without prohibiting any option or significantly changing their economic incentives (Rodriguez, 2018).

Figure 3. Sankey diagram with behavioral tools used and with potential for use in the covid-19 pandemic.

Source: Own elaboration in ATLAS.ti 9

Table 1. Research included in the systematic review

No.	Authors/ Year/ Title/ Source	Country of application	Main approach / Contribution	Approach / Technique
1	Lunn, P. et al. (2020). Motivating social distancing during the COVID-19 pandemic: An online experiment. Social Science & Medicine	Ireland	Communication strategies to promote social distancing. The study generates supporting evidence for communications that emphasize the impact of noncompliance on identifiable individuals and the potential to cause multiple infections.	Quantitative / Experimental and behavioral economics
	Saleska, J. and Choi, K. (2021). A behavioral economics perspective on the COVID-19 vaccine amid public mistrust. Translational Behavioral Medicine (TBM).	United States	Application of behavioral economics with respect to driving vaccination decision making in a context of distrust due to the speed of vaccine production and uncertainty about results / Behavioral economics concepts such as confirmation bias, negativity bias and optimism bias have been applied; the same that are present in the sample studied.	Quantitative / Documentary analysis (Secondary sources such as surveys)
	Ferchiou, A. et al. (2020). Individual Behaviors and COVID-19 Lockdown Exit Strategy: A Mid-Term Multidimensional Bio-economic Modeling Approach. Frontiers in Public Health.	France	Construction of a multidimensional bioeconomic model to simulate unlocking strategies considering age and transmission rate (Tr) to find combinations of scenarios that reduce economic losses, locked-in days, mortality and hospital saturation to a minimum cost. / Few differences were found between the scenarios, concluding that to address COVID-19, policies should focus on understanding the behavior of individuals, thus highlighting the need for behavioral economics.	Quantitative / Epidemiological Compartmental Model and Economic Optimization Model
	Wagner, C. et al. (2020). Economic and Behavioral Influencers of Vaccination and Antimicrobial Use. Frontiers in Public Health	United States	Review of factors contributing to vaccine underuse and antibiotic overuse. This will be useful in policy formulation. / Misperceptions about the risks of vaccine use and cognitive biases that reinforce such biases, as well as social norms of non-vaccination, push people to refuse or hesitate to vaccinate and over-consume antibiotics. This is of concern in the context of covid-19 where vaccines are newly manufactured.	Quantitative / Documentary analysis
5	Belizan, M. et al. (2020). Barriers to hypertension and diabetes management in primary health care in Argentina: qualitative research based on a behavioral economics approach. Translational	Argentina	To evaluate the public and private health systems, in order to raise the level of effectiveness in their intervention, creating public policies that minimize cognitive biases, which hinder the rapid care of chronic diseases.	Qualitative / Behavioral economics

	Behavioral Medicine (TBM)			
	Pérez, A. y Rodríguez, A. (2020). Economía del comportamiento y COVID-19: Una interpretación social de la realidad. Revista de Ciencias Sociales	Spain	Description of behavior from a behavioral economics perspective, with respect to measures to prevent the spread of COVID-19, which serves as a forward-looking model in a similar context / Highlights prevention and health promotion, where behavioral economics has ample potential for analysis to adjust public health policy decisions to help minimize the effects of a health crisis on individuals and the economy.	Qualitative / Documentary analysis (Analysis of information using the analytical-synthetic method for critical reading)
	Habersaat, K. et al. (2020). Ten considerations for effectively managing the COVID-19. Nature Human Behaviour.	States United	Ten considerations for communities to participate in the COVID-19 transition phase to a "new normal" are proposed. Understanding the impact that the pandemic and the imposition of restrictions has on people's daily lives, mental health, motivation, and intent to follow recommendations is critical to successful pandemic management, as well as a valuable source of information in preparing for future pandemics.	Qualitative / Interviews
	Si, H. et al. (2020) Uncovering people's mask-saving intentions and behaviors in the post-COVID-19 period: Evidence from China. Sustainable Cities and Society	China	Mask-saving behavior in medical resource sustainability and outbreak response / Mask-saving depends on several factors including perceived risk. If the shortage of medical resources in various countries were publicized, the public would be aware of the importance of saving existing medical resources.	Quantitative / partial least squares partial least squares structural equation modeling method of randomly collected questionnaires
	Plaksienko, V. et al. (2020). National trade and hospitality Industry in pandemic times: behavioral economics aspect. Economics and Finance	Ukraine	People's behaviors and choices to help formulate more effective public policies. It identifies biases in the decision-making process and uses them as entry points for interventions in particular behaviors. Behavioral economics has recently received much attention in public policymaking. This field of economics uses insights from the fields of psychology, neuroscience, and cognitive science to explain how people's behaviors deviate from rational choice theory and when and why people's short-term decisions sometimes undermine their long-term interests.	Quantitative / Documentary analysis (Secondary sources such as surveys)
	Ayres, I. et al. (2020). How to Make COVID-19 Contact Tracing Apps work: Insights from Behavioral Economics. Yale Law School, Public Law Research Paper Forthcoming.	London	Insights from behavioral science suggest that carefully crafted messages can induce people to engage in prosocial behavior. Contact Tracing Apps (CTAs) could, for example, notify people when they are in contact with too many people and could therefore be contributing to the spread of the virus. If this hypothesis is correct, CTAs could become a valuable communication channel between health authorities and the general public, which can be used to promote prudent behaviors.	Quantitative / Experimental and behavioral economics
	Soofi Moslem-Farid Najaf - Behzad	Switzerland	Behavioral economics can help policymakers identify people's decision biases and use them as starting points for designing COVID-19 preventive interventions. Behavioral economics interventions can help people behave rationally	Quantitative / Documentary analysis (Secondary)

	KaramiMatinUsing (2020) Insights from Behavioral Economics to Mitigate the Spread of COVID19		and make better COVID-19-related decisions.	sources such as surveys)
	Liu, Z. et al (2020). Exploring the mechanisms of influence on COVID-19 preventive behaviors in China's social media users	China	This study investigated the mechanisms through which emotional and cognitive processes resulting from the BIS (behavioral immune system) have promoted preventive behaviors in relation to COVID-19. Using data from the Sina Weibo platform, this study explored how the BIS triggered by COVID-19 influenced preventative behaviors. They measured their emotions (including disgust, happiness, and fear), cultural values (individualism and collectivism), moral concerns (including vice purity, vice fairness, and virtue authority) and behavioral intentions (including isolation intention, protection intention, and helping intention) using Text Mind software and related dictionaries.	Quantitative Tex Mind software and related dictionaries.
	Halpern Scoot, et al Miller. (2020). Cognitive Bias and Public Health Policy During the COVID-19 Pandemic	United States	They conduct an analysis of behavioral biases, consider biases or errors of human cognition that prioritize the easily imagined over the statistical, the present over the future, and the direct over the indirect. A better alternative would have been to implement policies of physical distancing, testing and tracing of past contacts that would have saved many more lives. Behaviorally informed policy formulation and communication is then necessary. They believe that an important goal of governance is to mitigate the effects of these and other biases in public policy and to effectively communicate the reasons for difficult decisions to the public. Rather than emphasizing aggressive medical interventions to counteract current disease cases, more effective messages would have focused on countering the spread of disease.	Qualitative. Observation.
	Robertson, C et al (2020). Indemnifying precaution: economic insights for regulation of a highly infectious disease. Journal of Law and the Biosciences	United States	How to align the costs and benefits of precautions so that precautions are taken sustainably! The moral hazard of health insurance, infectious diseases in agriculture and public health is examined, but that classical enforcement strategies to punish non-compliant individuals are hampered. From a behavioral theory, it is argued that one mechanism to address this problem is for policy makers to compensate individuals for the losses associated with adopting these socially desirable behaviors to reduce contagion.	Reflection
	Strickland, J. <i>et al.</i> (2021). Integrating Operant and Cognitive Behavioral Economics to Inform Infectious Disease Response: Prevention,	United States	This study has implications for the direct understanding of behavioral phenomena on the spread of COVID-19: social distancing, use of masks, obtaining evidence, and vaccination intentions. He believes that behavioral economics can provide robust policy-relevant data. Conclusions -They found that people are more likely to distance themselves socially when engaged in specific activities. Framing vaccine safety in a positive valence improves	Experimental Data collection sampling: Crowdsourcing

	Testing, and Vaccination in the COVID-19 Pandemic.		vaccine acceptance. The findings collectively show that mask use is highly sensitive to the social factors described by social discounting and behavioral economic procedures. Framing manipulations were found to impact the response pattern in the discounting and demand tasks used.	
	Hursh, S. <i>et al.</i> (2020). Quantifying the Impact of Public Perceptions on Vaccination Acceptance Using Behavioral Economics.	United States	This study was conducted to assess the impact of public perceptions of vaccine safety and efficacy on intention to seek COVID-19 vaccine using hypothetical scenarios of vaccine acceptance. Behavioral economics methodology could be used to inform future public health vaccination campaigns designed to influence public perceptions and improve public acceptance of the vaccine. Conclusions Hard data linking individual factors and vaccine messages to expected COVID-19 vaccination are critical for designing effective public health campaigns.	Quasi-experimental. Exponential demand mathematical functions
	Llonto C y Vela, L. (2021). Influencia de la economía del comportamiento para combatir el COVID-19	Global	Characterization of the use of behavioral economics to combat COVID 19, addressing an integrative literature review. The results indicate that policy makers use non-pharmaceutical interventions based on behavioral economics and psychology to reduce the transmission of infectious diseases. It has been determined that there are several behavioral tools to address behavioral biases for proper decision making, being nudging the main tool to counteract the cognitive costs of absorbing information in the spread of the COVID 19 virus; hence, the thematic approach has intersubjective elements typical of a qualitative research, so it is considered that it should be subjected to comparisons and scrutiny through various methods and approaches.	Qualitative documentary review
	Haushofer, J. (2020). Combining behavioral economics and infectious disease epidemiology to mitigate the COVID-19 outbreak.	Global	Using behavioral economics to address pandemic issues through a document review in a variety of contexts. They find that infectious disease transmission is temporally complex, but interventions are often assessed using snapshot measurements. This can lead to erroneous conclusions, and underscores the importance of careful measurement over time.	Qualitative documentary review

CONCLUSIONS

The studies reviewed confirm that in the fight against the pandemic, public policy makers have identified behavioral biases that have impeded rational decision making by individuals regarding vaccination, the use of personal protection mechanisms such as face masks and face shields, social distancing, dietary habits and physical activity. The behavioral biases identified were mainly loss aversion related to negativity bias in framing, representativeness heuristics, confirmation bias, present bias, negativity bias, over-optimism, availability heuristics, status quo or inertia bias and cognitive overload.

The tools with the greatest application to combat behavioral biases have been framing, communication mechanisms with graphics, which allow people to make better decisions because they observe how the images that show social distancing generate results; the use

of financial micro-incentives has been identified, such as government payments to those who comply with the instructions of social distancing or confinements or in kind for compliance with rules. There are also interventions that consider descriptive and prescriptive norms, as well as nudges and libertarian paternalism, which allow inducing people to make sensible decisions. Despite the importance of these tools, studies show the need for further scientific development of behavioral economics to incorporate the essentially dynamic nature of epidemics.

Regarding the work of researchers who provide evidence to public policy makers, the use of experimental designs and mainly quantitative studies has been identified, representing 61% of the cases analyzed.

Finally, there is evidence that behavioral economics has a substantial contribution to make in the fight against the epidemic and the scenario is serving to validate the theoretical developments of 2017 Nobel Laureate in Economics Richard H. Thaler.

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